

UDK 621.372.01

APPROXIMATION TECHNIQUES FOR MODELING AND ANALYSIS OF
ELECTRICAL CIRCUITS

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Abstract. *The nonlinearity of current–voltage characteristics represents a fundamental difficulty in the modeling and analysis of electronic circuits. Experimental data are typically available only in graphical form, whereas theoretical investigations require analytical representations. This paper analyzes commonly used approximation functions for nonlinear current–voltage characteristics and evaluates their applicability. Special attention is paid to polynomial, exponential, and hyperbolic functions. The study demonstrates that appropriate function selection significantly simplifies nonlinear circuit modeling while preserving acceptable accuracy.*

Keywords: *Nonlinear electrical circuits; current–voltage characteristics; function approximation; analytical modeling; exponential approximation; hyperbolic sine function.*

In practical electrical engineering, most electronic circuits contain nonlinear elements whose current–voltage characteristics cannot be described by linear relationships. The determination of an analytical dependence between current and voltage therefore becomes a key problem in circuit theory. Although experimental methods provide reliable graphical representations, analytical expressions are required for theoretical analysis, simulation, and mathematical modeling. At the same time, nonlinear circuit analysis is known to be substantially more complex than its linear counterpart, which motivates the search for efficient approximation approaches. It is known that any electronic circuit, in which the "reaction and the action are connected with nonlinear elements" is said to be non-linear [1]. The current-voltage characteristics of the circuit elements are usually determined as a result of the experiments conducted. The literature [1-3] shows a wide variety of graphical representations of CVC of different electronic circuit element. The results of the experiments are mainly represented in the form of graphs and in practical calculations graphical methods, piecewise-linear approximation, and others are widely used [1-3]. However, for theoretical study and analysis of electronic circuits an analytical representation of current-voltage characteristic for non-linear elements is required [1]. Therefore, an important practical issue of determining the analytical formulas describing the relationship between the current and the voltage in the circuit arises. On the other hand, ". . . analysis of nonlinear systems is mathematically much more difficult than the analysis of linear systems" [2].

In this regard, a need to study various approaches to this problem and to make a choice of the function types that allow the best approximation of the current-voltage characteristics of non-linear circuit elements arises.

Problem Statement. Due to the need for having explicit dependence of the current and voltage, expressed in the form of the equations of the CVC, to develop a mathematical model of the electronic circuits, it is required to determine the functional relationship between current and voltage.

In general, the electrical circuit contains not only elements that can to a sufficient degree of accuracy be considered linear, but explicit non-linear elements. Nonlinear elements differ in that their parameters (R , L , C) are functions of the voltage applied thereto. The equations of such circuits, derived on the basis of Kirchhoff's laws [1] will be non-linear. These equations are determined from the experimental results. They boil down to the graphical determination of the magnitude of the amount of current flowing in the circuit for several values of voltages and drawing a smooth curve for the currents.

Typically for this purpose, the approximation of the experimental data is used. In the literature [2-3] various types of approximating functions are proposed. It is advisable to conduct some analysis of the properties of these functions.

Experimental or statistical data are essential information for determining the analytical relationships between the variables (indicators) considered. It is required to determine the function that describes a relationship between these variables, which are in good agreement with the experimental [4] data.

This article analyzes the various options for approximating functions used to describe the functional dependence of the current on voltage. Also, unknown parameters, on which these functions depend, will be determined [5].

Transition to dimensionless variables. Before turning to the analysis of these functions, it is advisable to use a dimensionless values. The transition to dimensionless values and the use of dimensionless parameters in the calculations provide a certain convenience in solving the problem on a computer [6]. To transit to the dimensionless variables it is required to select the characteristic values for the task.

Let U_0 be some voltage, which is typical for the given component. Then $\frac{U_0}{R}$ can be the characteristic value of the current for a constant value of resistance. Transition to dimensionless values is performed by using the following formulas [7]:

$$x = \frac{u}{U_0}, \quad y = \frac{i \cdot R}{U_0} \quad (1)$$

Here x - the dimensionless stress, y - the dimensionless current.

Taking into account these formulas, the unknown approximating function can be written as follows: $i = \frac{U_0}{R} \cdot f(x)$ or $y = f(x)$. (2)

Here $f(x)$ is the unknown function, which determines the relationship between the dimensionless current and dimensionless voltage.

From the analysis of the existing methods of fitting the experimental data [2], it follows that the following functions are most commonly used:

- Linear function: $y = a \cdot x + b$, where a, b – the unknown parameters;
- Quadratic function: $y = a \cdot x^2 + b \cdot x + c$, where a, b, c – the unknown parameters;
- Exponential function: $y = a \cdot (1 - \exp(-\frac{x}{a}))$ (3)

and hyperbolic sine: $y = a \cdot sh \frac{x}{a}$. (4)

Linear and quadratic functions have been successfully used in many fields of science to approximate statistical or experimental data. However, the linear function of the form $y = a \cdot x + b$

is used only for linear circuits, and its use for the description of non-linear elements of electronic circuits is impractical. The quadratic function of the form $y = a \cdot x^2 + b \cdot x + c$. has been widely used.

The last two functions (3) and (4) are of particular interest, they can also be used for fitting the experimental data. Because the graphs of these functions are very similar to the graphs that represent the current-voltage characteristics of the various electrical circuit components. Many graphs of nonlinear element characteristics reported in the literature [1-3] have the same shapes, which are presented below in Figures 1 and 2 where the graphs of these functions are shown. Figure 1 shows the graphs when the current, with the voltage increasing, can tend to some constant value, and Figure 2 shows plots of the function for which the increase of the argument (voltage) leads to an unlimited increase in the values of the function (current).

These functions depend on the only unknown parameter a , whose value is to be determined. The values of the unknown parameters in the suggested functions of the approximation can be different for different components of the electronic circuit. To determine the numerical values of these unknown parameters, the experimental data and the well-known method of least squares are used.

The analysis shows that linear approximations are applicable only to linear circuit elements and are unsuitable for nonlinear components. Quadratic functions provide acceptable accuracy within limited voltage ranges. Exponential and hyperbolic sine functions demonstrate close qualitative agreement with experimentally observed current–voltage characteristics, including both saturation behavior and unbounded current growth. These functions require a small number of parameters, which can be reliably identified from experimental data.

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